

Finite Blocklength Analysis for SWIPT-Enabled RSMA Networks Under Realistic Assumptions

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Abstract—Efficient connectivity for energy constrained massive Internet of Things (IoT) nodes is among the key design challenges for future wireless networks. In this work, we analyze the downlink performance of a massive IoT network considering simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT). We consider the rate-splitting multiple access (RSMA) scheme in the finite blocklength (FBL) regime under realistic assumptions such as imperfect channel state information (CSI), imperfect successive interference cancellation (SIC), and hardware impairments in the energy harvesting circuitry. The system performance is assessed by evaluating closed-form expressions for the block-error rate (BLER) and goodput. We also derive analytical expressions for the average harvested energy considering linear and non-linear characteristics of the energy-constrained IoT nodes. The effect of the power splitting (PS) factor under linear and non-linear regimes on the BLER is also discussed. Monte Carlo simulations corroborate the accuracy of the derived expressions, which highlight the impact of increasing the blocklength and demonstrate the performance degradation generated by imperfect CSI, imperfect SIC, and hardware impairment. The results reveal that the integration of PS-SWIPT in RSMA networks can offer around 28% ~ 33% performance improvement in terms of BLER over SWIPT-enabled non-orthogonal multiple access networks.

Index Terms—BLER, energy harvesting, goodput, non-orthogonal multiple access, RSMA, SWIPT.

I. INTRODUCTION

BY 2030, our society is envisioned to be data-driven and sustainable enabled by near-instant wireless connectivity with Internet of Things (IoT) applications being at its centre [1]. This paradigm shift towards ubiquitous connectivity and seamless possibilities for digital experiences sets the stage for the emergence of sixth-generation (6G) wireless network [2]. Anticipated as an all-inclusive and intelligent communication ecosystem, 6G holds the potential to revamp industrial automation, autonomous vehicle mobility, extended reality (XR), and enhanced mobile broadband [3].

Many IoT applications usually require transmitting control information or measurement readings. Thus the transmission packets consists of a small payload. The conventional Shannon formula becomes inaccurate under the

short transmission packet regime, as it is designed for long blocklength, considering infinite time and resources for encoding and decoding. Considering this limitation, the authors in [4] developed an essential framework for finite blocklength (FBL) transmissions of short packets.

The ultra-reliable and low-latency communication (URLLC) service class was introduced to support XR, IoT, and other applications that adhere to strict decoding error probability, latency and end-to-end requirements. Since most URLLC applications operate in the FBL regime, their performance cannot be evaluate using the conventional Shannon limit formulas and analysis considering short-packet transmission becomes a necessity [5]. In particular, different authors have investigated the error probability and maximal achievable channel coding rate for blocklength as short as 100. Following [4], researchers have expanded upon this fundamental work to study various aspects of FBL communications [6]–[9]. For instance, in [6], the authors have demonstrated the joint convexity of the error probability at FBL against transmit power and blocklength within a specific region of interest.

Alongside transmission in the FBL regime, efficient utilization of the scarce radio resources is another challenge for emerging 6G applications requiring massive access. Innovative solutions are required to overcome the limitations of traditional orthogonal multiple access (OMA) schemes such as time division multiple access (TDMA), and orthogonal frequency-division multiple access (OFDMA) where the allocation of resources to the individual users are orthogonal [10]. In particular, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) and rate-splitting multiple access (RSMA) have arisen as promising techniques for 6G systems with the potential to improve interference management, spectral efficiency, and overall performance of the system [11]. Moreover, existing literature has shown the RSMA dominance over NOMA and space-division multiple access (SDMA) in terms of spectral efficiency, interference management, mobility, and latency [12].

In NOMA, superposition coding (SC) is employed at the transmitter side to encode multiple messages using different power levels into a single superimposed signal. At the receiver side, the users with stronger signals are decoded using successive interference cancellation (SIC) [13]. In contrast, in RSMA, the user data is first divided into multiple common and private parts. All the common parts are encoded into a single common stream and the multiple private parts are

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encoded into individual private streams. Finally, using SC all the parts are superimposed onto the same signal. At the receiving end, the common stream is first decoded with the help of a common codebook shared by all devices while treating private streams as interference. After successfully recovering the common stream, the device then executes SIC and decodes its own private stream. By smartly managing interference, the flexible transmission scheme of RSMA can deliver high spectral efficiency even under scenarios with imperfect channel state information (CSI) [14].

With sustainability being an important vision for 6G connectivity [15], simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) has evolved as a promising technology for low power consuming devices. SWIPT introduces the capability to simultaneously transmit data and harvest energy, enabling a more sustainable communication infrastructure for the next generation. Despite its attractive features, the performance of SWIPT-enabled RSMA networks under URLLC traffic has not been investigated so far. To unveil the full potential of these technologies, it is crucial to consider RSMA in URLLC applications where the devices are powered by SWIPT.

A. Related Works

The performance of NOMA schemes is well studied in the literature. For example, a simultaneous refracting/transmitting and reflecting reconfigurable intelligent surface-aided downlink NOMA system in the FBL regime was analyzed in [16]. The authors in [17] have analyzed the network performance by deriving the analytical expressions for outage probability and throughput considering imperfect SIC, hardware impairments and channel estimation errors for NOMA-enhanced overlay cognitive radio. In [18], the authors have studied how to increase the spectral efficiency of device-to-multi-device-aided cooperative networks and derived various performance metrics. In [19], the authors have jointly optimized the beam-forming vector and the used channel blocklength by proposing successive convex approximation algorithm and bisection method, respectively, for URLLC applications. Additionally, in [20], the authors have analyzed the system performance of cooperative-NOMA networks by deriving outage and throughput expressions for multiple distant IoT nodes considering imperfect SIC and also for a full-duplex enabled near user IoT node with non-linear energy harvesting (EH).

In contrast to NOMA, there is only a handful of papers investigating the more recently introduced multiple access scheme RSMA. The authors in [21] have studied a dynamic network resource selection problem by exploiting evolutionary games for mobile users in RSMA-enabled system. Moreover, an iterative algorithm based on successive convex approximation has been designed to optimize beamformers for both common and private messages among users within the same group. In [22], the authors have maximized the human type and machine type communication sum-rates by formulating a received signal strength based transmission

selection scheme. Moreover, the authors have introduced a deployment strategy based on RSMA while ensuring extensive network coverage of the considered system. Likewise, in [23] the authors have minimized the users' average latency by investigating the connection between wireless edge caching and RSMA. As it was a non-convex mixed-integer nonlinear programming problem, the authors resolved it using both the alternating optimization method and dynamic programming approach, separately. The authors in [24], have proposed an interesting study of flexible RSMA with FBL. In particular, the proposed flexible RSMA scheme makes the system capable of deciding whether SIC needs to be executed by a user or not. Likewise, the authors in [25] have maximized the sum-rate with FBL constraints by designing optimal linear precoders. The findings indicate that RSMA achieves the same transmission rate using shorter blocklengths when compared to NOMA and SDMA.

The concept SWIPT with and without NOMA has been investigated extensively in the literature. For example, in [26], the authors have analyzed the system performance by exploiting an overlay spectrum-sharing paradigm for a SWIPT-enabled non-linear power amplifier cooperative cognitive-radio sensor network. Moreover, the authors in [27] have minimized the transmit power consumption for a SWIPT-NOMA green cellular network by proposing a novel resource allocation scheme. In [28], the authors have derived analytical expressions for total harvested energy at each individual users and information rate of a SWIPT-enabled cell-free massive multiple-input-multiple-output system integrated with NOMA. Furthermore, a solution framework based on machine learning was developed to tackle the formulated non-convex and mixed combinatorial problem. In [29], the authors have investigated the system outage of NOMA in co-operative cognitive radio networks with SWIPT where the transmission power is harvested from the secondary transmitter by the cognitive relay. Additionally, few works exist on SWIPT-integrated RSMA. Nevertheless, the full possibilities of the SWIPT-integrated RSMA network at FBL remain to be investigated. For instance, the authors in [30], studied the multi-user multiple-input single-output SWIPT cognitive radio system with RSMA for information decoding and power splitting (PS) users. The proposed solution leverages the particle swarm optimization algorithm and the semidefinite relaxation technique with Gaussian randomization. In [31], the authors have optimized the common and private message beamforming and PS factor in order to maximize the EH and sum-rate at the users while reducing the inter-user interference.

B. Motivations and Contributions

To the best of our knowledge, none of the prior work has studied SWIPT-enabled RSMA downlink networks at FBL. *These have possible applications in IoT systems with the potential to improve connection quality and sustainability for FBL communications.* Specifically, by enabling EH in low-power IoT devices, SWIPT can reduce dependency on

Fig. 1: SWIPT-enabled RSMA Network at FBL.

frequent battery replacements, minimizing electronic waste and operational costs, which aligns with environmental, social and economic sustainability goals [32]. This motivates the contributions of this work. Specifically, we investigate the performance of a SWIPT-enabled RSMA network at FBL considering imperfect CSI, imperfect SIC¹, and hardware impairments. In particular, we exploit the transmitted RSMA-aided signal as a partial energy carrier by using power splitting (PS)-SWIPT considering linear and non-linear characteristics of the energy-constrained nodes. From sustainability perspective, the integration of SWIPT with RSMA for 6G network seems very promising for low power consuming IoT devices. However, we would like to highlight that the impact of the distance and the path-loss exponent factor on EH is extremely sensitive with respect to the circuit's linear or non-linear behavior as per our findings. Therefore, more findings related to the linear and non-linear EH circuits from hardware perspective is required. The main contributions of our work are as follows:

- We investigate the reliability of the considered network by deriving closed-form expressions of block-error rate (BLER) and goodput considering imperfect CSI, imperfect SIC and hardware impairments. Moreover, to understand the effect of these imperfections we have also computed the expressions considering perfect CSI, SIC and without hardware impairments. To get some beneficial insights of the system, we have further derived the asymptotic BLER expressions.
- Considering linear and non-linear characteristics of the EH circuit, we have derived the expressions for average power harvested at each user. Moreover, the effect of distance and path-loss coefficient on EH with respect to linear and non-linear circuit characteristics has been graphically highlighted.
- Our findings suggests that the larger blocklength with constant bits/slot, results in improved BLER. However,

¹This work investigates the one-layer RSMA. More complex schemes, such as hierarchical RSMA [11], also exist but are left for future work.

at the same time the system loses the essence of FBL transmissions. Therefore, important trade-off between both block-length and bits/slot are very essential for a desired system performance.

- We have demonstrated the superiority of SWIPT-enabled RSMA networks with imperfect SIC over SWIPT-enabled NOMA networks with perfect SIC case and SWIPT-enabled OMA networks. In addition to this, we have corroborated the accuracy of the derived analytical expressions using Monte-Carlo simulations.

C. Notations

The probability density function (PDF) and cumulative distribution function (CDF) for a random variable X are represented by $f_X(x)$ and $F_X(x)$, respectively. The notation $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ signifies a complex Gaussian distribution with a mean of zero and a variance of σ^2 . The parameters m and $\hat{\Omega}$ denote the shape and scale parameters associated with Nakagami- m fading, while $\Gamma(\cdot)$ and $\gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ refer to the Gamma function and the lower incomplete gamma function, respectively.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider a SWIPT-enabled RSMA downlink network as shown in Fig. 1 where a single-antenna BS communicates in FBL downlink mode with N single-antenna energy-constrained IoT nodes. As the BS uses RSMA to communicate simultaneously with N energy-constrained devices, it first divides the messages intended for these N devices into common parts and private parts. The common parts are encoded into a single common stream (α_c), which has to be decoded by all devices, while the private parts are encoded into N individual private streams (α_n), each intended for a specific device. The common and private streams are then superimposed and transmitted to the IoT devices.

In this work, we exploit the transmitted superimposed symbol as a partial energy carrier using PS-SWIPT as shown in Fig. 2. This figure illustrates the splitting mechanism

Fig. 2: RSMA receiving device architecture

where the received signal is passed through a PS-EH circuit. Subsequently, the message is transferred to the RSMA decoding unit, where the architecture initially recovers the common messages. Then, SIC is applied to cancel the common message and recover the private message. Finally, both the common and private messages are jointly fed into a message re-encoder to reconstruct the message originally transmitted by the BS. Therefore, the superimposed message transmitted by the BS can be expressed as $\alpha = \sqrt{P}\zeta_c\alpha_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \sqrt{P}\zeta_k\alpha_n$, where P denotes the transmit power available at the BS, with ζ_c and ζ_k denoting the fraction of P allocated to transmit α_c and α_k , respectively. The channel gain between the BS and n_{th} user is given by $h_n = \hat{h}_n + \tilde{h}_{er}$ where \hat{h}_n is the estimated channel gain and \tilde{h}_{er} is the channel estimation errors modeled as $\tilde{h}_{er} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \Omega_{h_{er}})$. As a result, $|h_n|$ and $|\hat{h}_n|$ follow the Nakagami- m distribution². Using [34], we define the channel estimation error variance as $\Omega_{h_{er}} = \Omega_n / (1 + \Xi\rho\Omega_n)$, where Ω_n is the variance of h_n , ρ denotes the transmitting signal to noise ratio (SNR), and $\Xi > 0$ is the quality parameter for channel estimation. Hence, the variance of $|\hat{h}_n|$ can be calculated as $\hat{\Omega}_n = (\Omega_n - \Omega_{h_{er}})$. Moreover, each device comprises an EH unit and an information decoding unit for simultaneous communication and EH purposes. Let, $\xi_n \in (0 \leq \xi_n \leq 1)$ be the PS factor for the received power at device n with $1 - \xi_n$ denoting the fraction of message power available after EH. Therefore, the harvested power considering linear EH at the n_{th} user can be calculated as

$$\psi_n = \delta \xi_n P |\hat{h}_n|^2, \quad (1)$$

where δ denotes the energy conversion efficiency. However, linear EH suffers few limitations because of threshold and sensitivity characteristics being not considered. Therefore, for a more practical scenario, we calculate the harvested power considering non-linear EH which can be calculated as

$$\Psi_n = \begin{cases} 0, & |\hat{h}_n|^2 < \frac{P_L}{\xi_n P}, \\ \psi_n, & \frac{P_L}{\xi_n P} \leq |\hat{h}_n|^2 \leq \frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}, \\ \delta P_H, & |\hat{h}_n|^2 > \frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where P_L and P_H denote the the minimum RF activation power and saturation power of the EH circuit, respectively. Considering this, the signal received at the n_{th} device for

²The Nakagami- m fading model encompasses Rician, Rayleigh, and Hoyt distributions as special cases [33].

TABLE I: Key Variables

Symbol	Definition
P	Transmit power at the base station
N	Number of downlink IoT devices
\hat{h}_n	Estimated channel gain
\tilde{h}_{er}	Channel estimation error
m_n	Shape parameter
Ω_n and $\hat{\Omega}_n$	Spread parameter under perfect and estimated CSI case
$\Omega_{h_{er}}$	Channel estimation error variance
α_c and ζ_c	Common stream and power allocated to it.
Ξ	Channel estimation quality parameter
α_n and ζ_n	Private stream for the n_{th} device and power allocated to it.
ρ	Signal to noise ratio
ξ_n	PS factor
δ	Energy conversion efficiency
κ_t^2 and κ_{rn}^2	Level of hardware impairment at the transmitter and receiver side
ϑ_n	Receiving antenna base-band additive white Gaussian noise
φ_n	Level of imperfection in SIC
$\Upsilon_{n,c}$ and $\Upsilon_{n,p}$	n_{th} device common and private SINR
$\varrho(\cdot)$	Blocklength
$\Lambda_{n,c}$ and $\Lambda_{n,p}$	n_{th} device common and private message BLER
$\hat{\Lambda}_{n,c}$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_{n,p}$	n_{th} device common and private message asymptotic BLER
$\Lambda_n^{c,p}$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_n^{c,p}$	n_{th} device final BLER and asymptotic BLER
\mathcal{G}_n	n_{th} device goodput
ς and τ	Reference path-loss value and Path-loss exponent factor
$\aleph_{n,c}$ and $\aleph_{n,p}$	Channel uses for training phase considering common and private messages
d_n	Distance between the transmitter and receiver

information decoding can be given by

$$y_n = (\hat{h}_n + \tilde{h}_{er}) \left((\sqrt{1 - \xi_n}) \left(\sqrt{P\zeta_c}x_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \sqrt{P\zeta_n}x_n \right) + \eta_t + \eta_{rn} \right) + (\sqrt{1 - \xi_n})\vartheta_n + w_n, \quad (3)$$

where $\eta_{tn} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, P\kappa_t^2)$, $\eta_{rn} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, P\kappa_{rn}^2)$ are the distortion noises with κ_t^2 and κ_{rn}^2 representing the level of hardware impairments³ at the transmitter and n_{th} receiver

³In practical wireless systems, hardware is subject to various types of imperfections, such as phase noise, imbalances in in-phase and quadrature components, and the nonlinearity of high-power amplifiers. Although these impairments are often addressed using compensation algorithms, some residual effects persist [35]. These imperfections negatively affect the system's performance. The parameters κ_t^2 and κ_{rn}^2 are used to represent the levels of these imperfections in the transmitter and receiver, respectively. These values correspond to the error vector magnitudes (EVMs), which are widely used to measure the quality of radio frequency transceivers. EVM is defined as the ratio of the mean distortion magnitude to the mean signal magnitude [35], [36].

$$\Upsilon_{n,c} = \frac{(1 - \xi_n) \zeta_c \rho |\hat{h}_n|^2}{\rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) |\hat{h}_n|^2 + \left(\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + \rho \Omega_{h_{er}} \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\zeta_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right) + 1} \quad (4)$$

$$\Upsilon_{n,p} = \frac{(1 - \xi_n) \zeta_n \rho |\hat{h}_n|^2}{\rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq n}}^N \zeta_j + \varphi_n \zeta_c \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) |\hat{h}_n|^2 + \left(\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + \rho \Omega_{h_{er}} \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\varphi_n \zeta_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right) + 1} \quad (5)$$

side, respectively, $\vartheta_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2)$ denotes the device's receiving antenna base-band additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN), and $w_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_n^2)$ denotes the sampled AWGN due to base-band signal conversion.

At the device end, the common stream is first decoded considering all the private streams as interference. Thus, the received signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR) at the n th device to decode α_c from y_n can be given as (4) written on top of the next page, where $\rho = P/\sigma_n^2$. After successfully decoding and subtracting the common stream from y_n using SIC, the device will try to decode its own private stream α_n , treating all other private streams as interference. However, in practice, perfect SIC may not be assured resulting in some residual interference from α_c . Hence, the n th device will decode its own private stream α_n with the SINR of (5), where $\varphi_n \in (0, 1)$ represents the level of imperfection in SIC post decoding α_c [37].

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we analyze the performance of the SWIPT-enabled RSMA network with FBL by deriving closed-form expressions for the BLER and the goodput. Next, we derive the expressions for average power harvested considering linear and non-linear EH. Moreover, as $|\hat{h}_n|$ is Nakagami- m distributed therefore, $|\hat{h}_n|^2$ follows a Gamma distribution whose PDF and CDF are given as

$$f_{|\hat{h}_n|^2}(y) = \frac{m_n^{m_n} y^{m_n-1}}{\hat{\Omega}_n^{m_n} \Gamma(m_n)} \exp\left(-\frac{m_n}{\hat{\Omega}_n} y\right), \quad y \geq 0. \quad (6)$$

$$F_{|\hat{h}_n|^2}(y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m_n)} \gamma\left(m_n, \frac{m_n}{\hat{\Omega}_n} y\right), \quad y \geq 0. \quad (7)$$

A) *BLER Analysis:* The BLER at n th device for decoding the common and private streams for ϱ_b channel uses and ω_b bits/slot when $\varrho_b > 100$ can be approximated as [38],

$$\Lambda_n^{c,p} \approx \mathbb{E} \left\{ Q \left(\frac{C(\Upsilon_b) - r_b}{\sqrt{V(\Upsilon_b)/\varrho_b}} \right) \right\}, \quad (8)$$

where $b \in \{\{n, c\}, \{n, p\}\}$, $C(\Upsilon_b) = \log_2(1 + \Upsilon_b)$ is the Shannon capacity, $r_b = \omega_b/\varrho_b$ and $V(\Upsilon_b)$ is the channel dispersion that measures the stochastic channel variability relative to a deterministic channel having the same capacity

which is calculated as $(1 - (1 + \Upsilon_b)^{-2}) (\log_2 e)^2$. The respective BLER is evaluated in the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *The BLER at the n th device considering imperfect CSI, imperfect SIC, and hardware impairments can be evaluated as*

$$\Lambda_n^{c,p} \approx \Lambda_{n,c} + \Lambda_{n,p} - (\Lambda_{n,c} \times \Lambda_{n,p}), \quad (9)$$

where $\Lambda_{n,c}$ is given in (10), $\Lambda_{n,p}$ is given in (11), $\vartheta_b = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2^{2r_b}-1}}$, $\beta_b = 2^{r_b} - 1$, $\Phi_b = \beta_b - \frac{1}{2\vartheta_b\sqrt{\varrho_b}}$, and $\Theta_b = \beta_b + \frac{1}{2\vartheta_b\sqrt{\varrho_b}}$.

Proof. Refer to Appendix A. ■

Corollary 1. *The BLER at the n th device considering perfect CSI, SIC, and no hardware impairments can be obtained by substituting high 'Ξ' values, $\varphi_n = 0$, and $\kappa_{rn}^2 = \kappa_t^2 = 0$, respectively, for calculating $\Omega_{h_{er}}$ in (9).*

Theorem 2. *The asymptotic BLER at the n th device considering imperfect SIC, and hardware impairments can be evaluated as*

$$\hat{\Lambda}_n^{c,p} \approx \hat{\Lambda}_{n,c} + \hat{\Lambda}_{n,p} - (\hat{\Lambda}_{n,c} \times \hat{\Lambda}_{n,p}), \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\Lambda}_{n,c}$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_{n,p}$ are given in (13) and (14), respectively.

Proof. Refer to Appendix B. ■

Corollary 2. *By applying steps outlined in Corollary 1, the asymptotic BLER at the n th device with perfect CSI, SIC, and no hardware impairments can be obtained.*

B) *Goodput Analysis:* Evaluated in nats per channel use (npcu) it is defined as a useful communication rate when data or frames considering total channel uses (ϖ_{tot}^b) for data communication and training phase are delivered successfully over the network [39].

Theorem 3. *The goodput at the n th device under imperfect CSI, imperfect SIC, and hardware impairment can be expressed as*

$$\mathcal{G}_n = \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{\varpi_{tot}^{n,c}} \right) r_{n,c} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\varpi_{tot}^{n,p}} \right) r_{n,p} \right] (1 - \Lambda_n^{c,p}), \quad (15)$$

where $\varpi_{tot}^{n,c} = \varrho_{n,c} + \aleph_{n,c}$ and $\varpi_{tot}^{n,p} = \varrho_{n,p} + \aleph_{n,p}$ with \aleph_b denoting the channel uses for training phase.

$$\Lambda_{n,c} \approx \frac{\vartheta_{n,c} \sqrt{\varrho_{n,c}} (\Theta_{n,c} - \Phi_{n,c})}{\Gamma(m_n)} \gamma \left(m_n, \frac{m_n ((\Theta_{n,c} + \Phi_{n,c})/2) \left[\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + \rho \Omega_{h_{er}} \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\zeta_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right] + 1}{\hat{\Omega}_n \rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \zeta_c - ((\Theta_{n,c} + \Phi_{n,c})/2) \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right)} \right). \quad (10)$$

$$\Lambda_{n,p} \approx \frac{\vartheta_{n,p} \sqrt{\varrho_{n,p}} (\Theta_{n,p} - \Phi_{n,p})}{\Gamma(m_n)} \gamma \left(m_n, \frac{m_n ((\Theta_{n,p} + \Phi_{n,p})/2) \left[\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + \rho \Omega_{h_{er}} \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\varphi_n \zeta_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right] + 1}{\hat{\Omega}_n \rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \zeta_n - ((\Theta_{n,p} + \Phi_{n,p})/2) \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq n}}^N \zeta_j + (1 - \xi_n) \varphi_n \zeta_c + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right)} \right). \quad (11)$$

$$\hat{\Lambda}_{n,c} \approx \frac{\vartheta_{n,c} \sqrt{\varrho_{n,c}} (\Theta_{n,c} - \Phi_{n,c})}{\Gamma(m_n) \times m_n} \left(\frac{m_n ((\Theta_{n,c} + \Phi_{n,c})/2) \left[\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + 1 \right]}{\hat{\Omega}_n \rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \zeta_c - ((\Theta_{n,c} + \Phi_{n,c})/2) \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right)} \right)^{m_n}. \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{\Lambda}_{n,p} \approx \frac{\vartheta_{n,p} \sqrt{\varrho_{n,p}} (\Theta_{n,p} - \Phi_{n,p})}{\Gamma(m_n) \times m_n} \left(\frac{m_n ((\Theta_{n,p} + \Phi_{n,p})/2) \left[\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + 1 \right]}{\hat{\Omega}_n \rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \zeta_n - ((\Theta_{n,p} + \Phi_{n,p})/2) \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq n}}^N \zeta_j + (1 - \xi_n) \varphi_n \zeta_c + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right)} \right)^{m_n}. \quad (14)$$

Corollary 3. Note that by substituting $\varphi_n = 0$, $\kappa_{rn}^2 = \kappa_t^2 = 0$ and high 'Ξ' values for calculating $\Omega_{h_{er}}$, the \mathcal{G}_n for perfect case can be evaluated.

Theorem 4. The average power harvested at the n_{th} device considering non-linear EH can be expressed as

$$\Psi_n^{avg} = \delta \xi_n P \left[\frac{\hat{\Omega}_n}{m_n \Gamma(m_n)} \left[\Gamma \left(m_n + 1, \frac{m_n \frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}}{\hat{\Omega}_n} \right) - \left[\Gamma \left(m_n + 1, \frac{m_n \frac{P_L}{\xi_n P}}{\hat{\Omega}_n} \right) \right] \right] + \frac{P_H \delta}{\Gamma(m_n)} \Gamma \left(m_n, \frac{m_n \frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}}{\hat{\Omega}_n} \right) \right]. \quad (16)$$

Proof. Refer to Appendix C. ■

Remark 1. By substituting $P_H = \infty$ and $P_L = 0$ in (16), the average power harvested at the n_{th} device using linear EH can be obtained.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we present Monte Carlo simulations to validate the accuracy of the derived analytical expressions. For the simulations, a distance-dependent path-loss model is adopted [40], which is calculated as ς/d_j^τ , where $j \in \text{BS-}n_{th}$ device, with ς representing the reference path-loss

value set at 1 meter, $d_{(\cdot)}$ denoting the distance between the transmitter and the receiver, and $\tau = 3.7$ representing the path-loss exponent factor. This τ value is aligned

TABLE II: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
m_1	3	ξ_n	0.5	$\sigma_n^2 = \sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2$ [34]	-100 dB
ζ_c	0.6	ζ_1	0.15	ζ_2	0.25
δ	0.8	BS - D_1	60m	BS - D_2	63m
ϱ_b	500, [38]	ω_b	50, [38]	m_2	3

with shadowed urban cellular radio environments, where the path-loss exponent typically varies from 3 to 5 [41]. This choice was made to model challenging propagation conditions typical of urban settings and to explore the impact of these parameters on energy harvesting capabilities and overall system performance. Moreover, the channel estimation error variance is computed using the formula outlined in Section (II), and for simulating BLER, we use the expression in (8) from Section (III). Unless otherwise specified, all other parameters used for the simulations are provided in Table II. The results from these simulations offer valuable insights into the factors influencing system performance under FBL conditions. Furthermore, we have considered two user devices, namely D_1 and D_2 , for the simulations. However, all the derived analytical expressions

Fig. 3: BLER versus ρ with imperfect CSI.

Fig. 4: BLER versus P with imperfect SIC and hardware impairment.

are valid for N devices.

Fig. 3 demonstrates the impact of channel estimation quality parameter (Ξ) on BLER ($\Lambda_n^{c,p}$) of D_1 and D_2 for varying transmit SNR (ρ) available at the BS considering perfect SIC and ideal hardware impairment. It can be noticed that the derived analytical expression in (9) for $\Lambda_n^{c,p}$ is in close agreement with the simulations. Moreover, $\Lambda_1^{c,p}$ and $\Lambda_2^{c,p}$ improves proportionally with an increasing ρ . In addition to this, one can also observe the degrading impact on the BLER performance for lower values of Ξ . For example, when $\Xi \rightarrow 0.2$, $\Lambda_1^{c,p} = 9.81 \times 10^{-5}$ and $\Lambda_2^{c,p} = 3.05 \times 10^{-5}$ at $\rho \approx 17.1$ dBm. However, the same performance for D_1 and D_2 is achieved with 18.13% and 33% lesser power with $\rho \approx 14.1$ dBm and ≈ 11.5 dBm when $\Xi \rightarrow 0.7 \rightarrow \infty$, i.e, towards perfect CSI, respectively. Furthermore, the asymptotic BLER analysis coincides with the simulation and analytical lines at high SNR which validates the accuracy of the analytical expression in (12). These results emphasize the critical role of channel estimation quality in enhancing power efficiency for FBL communication networks, especially in scenarios where power resources are constrained or where high signal clarity is essential to maintain network performance.

Fig. 4 depicts the effect of imperfect SIC and hardware impairments on $\Lambda_1^{c,p}$ and $\Lambda_2^{c,p}$ against varying ρ considering perfect CSI. Interestingly, when we compare Fig. 3 perfect CSI performance with Fig. 4, an extra 6.7% and 10.3% of power is required to achieve the same BLER performance when imperfect SIC (φ_n) is 10% and hardware impairment from the transmitter and receiver ($\kappa_t^2 + \kappa_n^2$) is 0.1. In addition to this, it can also be noticed that hardware impairment has a more degrading impact on $\Lambda_1^{c,p}$ and $\Lambda_2^{c,p}$ than the imperfect SIC. From the perspective of energy efficiency, understanding the power increase requirement to offset the effects of hardware impairments and imperfect SIC can be vital for energy management strategies.

Fig. 5 shows the goodput (\mathcal{G}_n) behaviour of D_1 and D_2 with varying ρ considering perfect CSI for different

blocklength (ϱ_b) values with the channel uses for training phase, $N_b = 200$, $\kappa_t^2 = \kappa_{r1}^2 = \kappa_{r2}^2 = 0.05$, and $\varphi_1 = \varphi_2 = 10\%$. The derived analytical expression for \mathcal{G}_n in (15) is closely matching with the simulations. It can be observed that \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 increases as bits/slot (ω_b) increases for a fixed ϱ_b . Furthermore, \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 also increases when ϱ_b is reduced keeping ω_b constant. For example, for $\omega_b = 50$ and $\varrho_b = 800$, \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 saturates at 0.125 npcu for $\rho \geq 3$ dBm. However, when $\varrho_b = 500$, \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 increases and saturates at 0.2 npcu for $\rho \geq 6$ dBm considering same ω_b . Furthermore, when $\omega_b = 80$ and $\varrho_b = 500$, \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 further increases and saturates at 0.35 npcu for $\rho \geq 11$ dBm. The reason for this different saturation level is due to the fulfillment of the target rate which is dependent on r_b . In addition to this, \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 remain negligible for lower ρ values. However, as expected it gradually start to increase for an increasing ρ and attains maximum goodput. This improvement occurs as the blocklength decreases from 800 to 500, while the number of information bits remains constant at $\omega_b = 50$. Thus, even though the blocklength is shorter, the density of the transmitted information remains high, enhancing the system's efficiency.

Fig. 6 demonstrates the impact of \mathcal{G}_n with respect to an increasing blocklength for $\kappa_t^2 = \kappa_{r1}^2 = \kappa_{r2}^2 = 0.05$, $\varphi_1 = \varphi_2 = 10\%$, $\omega_b = 90$ and $N_b = 200$ considering imperfect SIC, hardware impairments and different values of Ξ . It can be observed that \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 first increases with an increasing ϱ_b up to a certain limit and then starts getting saturated for higher values of ϱ_b , i.e, when $\varrho_b \geq 10000$ for $\Xi \rightarrow \infty$ and $\Xi \rightarrow 0.9$ at $\rho = -9$ dBm and $\rho = -4.5$ dBm, respectively. The reason for this behaviour is because of the lower value of ω_b with respect to ϱ_b resulting in lower r_b . Interestingly, the saturation of \mathcal{G}_n under high ϱ_b values points to an inefficiency that emerges due to longer frame durations that do not effectively contribute to higher goodput beyond a certain threshold. This observation suggests that while increasing blocklength can initially improve goodput by allowing more

Fig. 5: Goodput versus P .

Fig. 6: Goodput versus Blocklength.

Fig. 7: RSMA versus NOMA and OMA.

Fig. 8: BLER and EH versus ξ_n .

bits to be processed per frame, there is a diminishing return effect as the frame duration becomes a bottleneck. Moreover, the insights into the impact of Ξ on performance reveal significant variations in goodput depending on the quality of channel estimation. For example, at $\rho = -9$ dBm and $\rho_b = 8000$, \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 achieve considerably higher values when $\Xi \rightarrow \infty$ compared to when $\Xi \rightarrow 0.9$. This illustrates the critical role of accurate channel estimation in achieving optimal network performance and maintaining efficiency in data transmission. Furthermore, the need to double ρ from -9 dBm to -4.5 dBm to achieve comparable goodput under lesser channel estimation accuracy underscores the increased energy requirement associated with compensating for imperfect CSI.

Fig. 7 illustrates the BLER performance versus transmit SNR ρ for RSMA, NOMA, and OMA based on simulations. For the two-user NOMA scenario, we use 200 bits/slot with a blocklength of 500, while for OMA, we allocate 100 bits/slot per user with the blocklength equally divided among the users. The rationale behind these settings is as follows: In RSMA, we allocate 50 bits/slot for the common

stream and 50 bits/slot for each private stream (D_1 and D_2), totaling 150 bits/slot, where the total number of bits specific to an individual user is 100. Unlike RSMA, where common and private streams are multiplexed, NOMA does not split transmissions into separate streams, leading to a higher effective rate per channel use. The results show that RSMA consistently outperforms both NOMA and OMA, even in the presence of hardware impairments, for a blocklength of 500 and $\omega_b = 50$. For example, at $\rho = 10$ dBm with $\kappa_t^2 = \kappa_{rn}^2 = 0.05$, the BLER values for RSMA are 6.12×10^{-4} for D_1 and 1.73×10^{-4} for D_2 . Under the same conditions, for NOMA with $\kappa_t^2 = \kappa_{rn}^2 = 0$, the BLER increases to 6.7×10^{-4} for D_1 and 1.71×10^{-3} for D_2 . In contrast, OMA exhibits significantly worse performance, with BLER values of 1.55×10^{-2} for D_1 and 4.7×10^{-3} for D_2 . The degradation in OMA stems from the resource split, which reduces the available blocklength, and rate per channel use (r_b), thereby negatively impacting the BLER of D_1 and D_2 .

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 shows the analytical BLER behavior of D_1 and D_2 in addition with the energy harvested by

Fig. 9: BLER and EH versus ξ_n .

them considering different distance, τ , channel estimation errors, and imperfect SIC for different values of PS factor (ξ_n). It can be observed that $\Lambda_1^{c,p}$ and $\Lambda_2^{c,p}$ degrades with an increasing ξ_n . Moreover, one can also observe the impact of ξ_n on BLERs when $\Xi \rightarrow 0.6$, $\varphi_n = 0\%$ and further towards perfect CSI and SIC case alternatively. In addition to that, the relation of ξ_n value with $\Lambda_1^{c,p}$ and $\Lambda_2^{c,p}$ is also evident from the plot. For example, in Fig. 8 the BLER of 10^{-6} for the parameters summarized in Table. II is achieved only when $\varphi_n \leq 0.5$. Otherwise, the desired performance for the system will not be fulfilled. Furthermore, D_1 and D_2 only harvest a small amount of energy that too linearly. However, in Fig. 9 when $d_1 = 30\text{m}$, $d_2 = 33\text{m}$ and $\tau = 3.1^4$, one can notice a drastic improvement in $\Lambda_1^{c,p}$, $\Lambda_2^{c,p}$ and EH with D_1 and D_2 being capable of EH exhibiting linear and non-linear characteristics. Furthermore, a saturation in non-linear EH of D_1 can be seen. The reason for this behaviour is due to the value of P_H . Lastly from the graph, two main takeaways can be noticed (i) PS-SWIPT for RSMA networks is beneficial only when the devices are not very far away from the transmitting source or the pathloss between the transmitter and receiver is low. (ii) Depending on the distance and pathloss one can get idea what type EH circuit should be deployed, i.e, linear or non-linear. If the transmitter and receiver are quite far apart then integration of PS-SWIPT with RSMA aided networks will only increase the system complexity resulting in no actual benefits.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This work analyzed the system performance at FBL for a SWIPT-enabled RSMA-aided-downlink network considering channel estimation errors, imperfect SIC, and hardware impairments. We have first derived the analytical expressions for BLER and goodput under both perfect and imperfect CSI, SIC, and hardware impairments. Then, we have obtained the expression for the average harvested power for

⁴This value also closely resembles the complex propagation conditions typical of real-world urban settings [41].

both linear and non-linear EH models. Furthermore, the channel estimation quality parameter, imperfect SIC, and hardware impairments effect on the system performance has been highlighted. In some cases, lower value of the channel estimation quality parameter might lead to more than 100% extra power consumption. Moreover, hardware impairments degrades the system performance more when compared with imperfect SIC factor while having the same numerical level of distortions. Finally, a fair comparison between SWIPT-enabled RSMA and SWIPT-enabled NOMA has been demonstrated showing a 28% ~ 33% performance difference with RSMA outperforming the NOMA system even with imperfect SIC and hardware impairments over perfect SIC and ideal hardware impairment case for NOMA. Lastly, the effect of PS-SWIPT, and linear and non-linear device characteristics has been highlighted by showing the impact of distance and pathloss exponent on EH and BLER. These findings are significant for the design and operation of energy-efficient wireless RSMA networks, especially in industrial environments where power efficiency and reliable communication are paramount. We would like to highlight that this analysis can easily be extended for simultaneous reflecting and transmitting (STAR)-RIS as possible future work, thus, revealing the usefulness of this physical layer technology in enhanced system performance and EH while analyzing the impact of hardware impairments in RIS/STAR-RIS.

APPENDIX A

Proof. In order to derive n_{th} device instantaneous BLER, we first need to evaluate the common and private stream BLER separately. Thus, for common stream the BLER at the n_{th} device can be evaluated as

$$\Lambda_{n,c} \approx \mathbb{E} \left\{ Q \left(\frac{C(\Upsilon_{n,c}) - r_{n,c}}{\sqrt{V(\Upsilon_{n,c})/\varrho_{n,c}}} \right) \right\}, \quad (17)$$

Using piece-wise linear approximation we evaluate (17) as $Q \left(\frac{C(\Upsilon_{n,c}) - r_{n,c}}{\sqrt{V(\Upsilon_{n,c})/\varrho_{n,c}}} \right) \simeq \Delta_{n,c}(\Upsilon_{n,c})$ which is given as (21) written on top of the next page. Next, by taking the mean of $\Delta_{n,c}(\Upsilon_{n,c})$ characterized by the PDF of $\Upsilon_{n,c}$ and then applying integration by parts we simplify (21) as

$$\Lambda_{n,c} \approx \vartheta_{n,c} \sqrt{\varrho_{n,c}} \int_{\Phi_{n,c}}^{\Theta_{n,c}} F_{\Upsilon_{n,c}}(y) dy. \quad (18)$$

Now, solving the integral involved in (18) using the Riemann integral approach as $\int_a^b g(y) dy = (a-b)g((a+b)/2)$, we obtain

$$\Lambda_{n,c} \approx \vartheta_{n,c} \sqrt{\varrho_{n,c}} (\Theta_{n,c} - \Phi_{n,c}) F_{\Upsilon_{n,c}}((\Theta_{n,c} + \Phi_{n,c})/2), \quad (19)$$

where $F_{\Upsilon_{n,c}}$ is the CDF of (4). In order to evaluate (19), we first calculate the CDF of $\Upsilon_{n,c}$ as

$$F_{\Upsilon_{n,c}}(y) = \Pr(\Upsilon_{n,c} < y) \quad (20)$$

Substituting (4) in (20) and doing some algebraic manipulations, we get (22). Next, using (19) and (22), we obtain (23). Lastly, substituting (7) in (23), we obtain the common stream BLER as (10). Using a similar approach from (17)

$$\Delta_{n,c}(\Upsilon_{n,c}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \Upsilon_{n,c} \leq \Phi_{n,c}, \\ 0.5 - \vartheta_{n,c}\sqrt{\varrho_{n,c}}(\Upsilon_{n,c} - \beta_{n,c}), & \Phi_{n,c} \leq \Upsilon_{n,c} \leq \Theta_{n,c} \\ 0, & \Upsilon_{n,c} \geq \Theta_{n,c}, \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$F_{\Upsilon_{n,c}}(y) = \Pr \left(|\hat{h}_n|^2 < \frac{y \left(\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + \rho \Omega_{h_{er}} \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\zeta_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right) + y}{\rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \zeta_c - y \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right)} \right) \\ = F_{|\hat{h}_n|^2} \left(\frac{y \left(\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + \rho \Omega_{h_{er}} \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\zeta_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right) + y}{\rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \zeta_c - y \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right)} \right). \quad (22)$$

$$\Lambda_{n,c} \approx \vartheta_{n,c}\sqrt{\varrho_{n,c}}(\Theta_{n,c} - \Phi_{n,c})F_{|\hat{h}_n|^2} \left(\frac{\left((\Theta_{n,c} + \Phi_{n,c})/2 \right) \left[\sigma_{\vartheta_n}^2 (1 - \xi_n) + \rho \Omega_{h_{er}} \left((1 - \xi_n) \left(\zeta_c + \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n \right) + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right] + 1}{\rho \left((1 - \xi_n) \zeta_c - ((\Theta_{n,c} + \Phi_{n,c})/2) \left((1 - \xi_n) \sum_{n=1}^N \zeta_n + \kappa_{rn}^2 + \kappa_t^2 \right) \right)} \right). \quad (23)$$

to (10) the BLER for the private stream can be obtained as (11). ■

APPENDIX B

Proof. In order to derive n_{th} device asymptotic BLER, we first need to evaluate the common and private stream asymptotic BLER separately as described from (17) to (23). Next, as $\rho \rightarrow \infty$, the term $\Omega_{h_{er}}$ becomes negligible or any value of $\Xi > 0$. Next, we use $\gamma(a, z) \underset{z \rightarrow 0}{\approx} \frac{z^a}{a}$, thus, we obtain (13) and (14) for common and private message, respectively. Finally, using (13) and (14), we get (12). ■

APPENDIX C

Proof. As (2) can be reformulated as [42],

$$\Psi_n^{avg} = \delta \xi_n P \int_{\frac{P_L}{\xi_n P}}^{\frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}} w f_{|\hat{h}_n|^2}(w) dw + \delta P_H \int_{\frac{P_L}{\xi_n P}}^{\frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}} f_{|\hat{h}_n|^2}(w) dw, \quad (24)$$

where $f_{|\hat{h}_n|^2}(w)$ is given in (6). After, performing few mathematical manipulations and using [43, 3.351.2], $\int_{\frac{P_L}{\xi_n P}}^{\frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}} w f_{|\hat{h}_n|^2}(w) dw$ and $\int_{\frac{P_L}{\xi_n P}}^{\frac{P_H}{\xi_n P}} f_{|\hat{h}_n|^2}(w) dw$ can be obtained. Finally, substituting all the values in (24), we get (16). ■

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